

MEDICAL SCIENCES

TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DENTOALVEOLAR ANOMALIES AND PHONETIC DISORDERS

Mehmani I.

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medical assistant
Department of Orthodontics*

Mehmani V.

*Azerbaijan Medical University, assistant
Department of Orthodontics*

Ashrafov D.

*Department of Orthopedic Dentistry. Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University. Baku.*

Abstract

Children with phonetic disorders are observed during examination of orthodontic patients. Only elimination of anatomical defects does not lead to normalization of sound articulation. This requires close cooperation between the orthodontist and speech therapist, if necessary, with the involvement of specialists of other profiles.

Keywords: anomalies and deformations of the dentoalveolar apparatus, phonetic disorders, a complex of diagnostic and therapeutic measures.

Children with phonetic disorders are observed during examination of orthodontic patients, which are manifested in the replacement, distortion or complete absence of certain sounds in oral speech [1–4]. Anomalies and deformations of the maxillofacial region interfere with normal articulation of sounds, complicating their speech therapy correction [1]., 4–6]. Studying the objective state of the respiratory tract is an additional factor in the successful correction of phonetic disorders [7–11]. It is well known that the elimination of anatomical defects alone does not lead to the normalization of sound articulation [4]. This requires close cooperation between an orthodontist and a speech therapist, if necessary, with the involvement of specialists of other profiles [5, 12].

Materials and methods of research

To develop a diagnostic and therapeutic complex, 160 children with existing and absent anomalies and deformations of the dentoalveolar system were examined. Of these, 86 children aged 6 to 12 years with anomalies and deformations of the dentoalveolar system and 74 children (24 aged 3 to 6 years, 50 aged 6 to 12 years) without orthodontic pathology. The work studied the relationship between dentoalveolar anomalies and otolaryngological pathology. Among those examined, 155 children with normal hearing but impaired pronunciation were identified, which became a further step in studying phonetic changes in speech depending on the forms of dental anomalies.

A total of 82 children aged 6 to 12 years (38 with complicated distal deep, 16 with distal, 18 with open, 10 with mesial bite). The following research methods were used: clinical; rhinocopy, pharyngoscopy, otoscopy, tone and speech audiometry, tympanometry; anthropometric measurements of scanned jaw models, cephalometry, electromyography, cone-beam computed tomography; the semiotic component of speech was studied, statistical. Only the elimination of anatomical defects does not lead to the normalization of sound articulation. This requires close cooperation between

an orthodontist and a speech therapist, if necessary, with the involvement of specialists of other profiles.

Research objective: to propose and evaluate the effectiveness of a set of diagnostic and therapeutic measures in patients with dentoalveolar anomalies and deformations, which were accompanied by phonetic disorders.

Research material and methods. 160 children with existing and absent anomalies and deformations of the dentoalveolar system were examined. The following research methods were used: clinical; rhinoscopy, pharyngoscopy, otoscopy, tone and speech audiometry, tympanometry; anthropometry, cephalometry, electromyography, computed tomography; the semiotic component of speech was studied, statistical. Research results and their discussion. It was confirmed that otolaryngological diseases are an additional risk factor for the formation of dentoalveolar anomalies and a factor aggravating orthodontic treatment. Phonetic changes in dentoalveolar anomalies were studied. Removable and non-removable equipment was used to eliminate orthodontic pathology. Most patients were diagnosed with narrowing of the jaws in the lateral areas, which leads to forced retention of the tongue in the lower back position. Standard Dr. vestibular plates were additionally used. Hinz – MUPPY-P» with beads, removable orthodontic appliances, Bluegrass appliances and the proposed devices for the elimination and prevention of harmful language habits. The proposed device promotes training of the muscular structures of the articulatory apparatus. A set of diagnostic and therapeutic measures allows to increase the effectiveness of orthodontic treatment of children with dental anomalies due to a multidisciplinary approach.

Results and discussion During the examination the following was established: adenoiditis of I–III degree in 125 children (80.6%), of which 19 (12.2%) had degree II and 11 (7.1%) had degree II–III, hypertrophy of the palatine tonsils in 77 children (49.6%), of which 48 (30.9%) had degree II and 30 (19.3%) had degree II–

III, and a characteristic adenoid breathing pattern – closed nasal mucus. Taking into account the obtained data, it was assumed that otolaryngological diseases are an additional risk factor for the development of dentoalveolar anomalies and a factor complicating orthodontic treatment. It is advisable to treat otolaryngological diseases before orthodontic correction. To exclude from the study group children with hearing impairments who subsequently needed the help of an audiologist, additional research methods were used. %, distal - 62.9%, medial - 80.6%, open - in 97.1%. We studied phonetic changes in dentoalveolar anomalies. An assessment was made using the speech therapy examination card. In the absence of orthodontic pathology in children under 4-6 years old, the pronunciation of sibilants and hissing sounds suffered most, but for this age group, the replacement or omission of sounds is a variant of the physiological norm; in children aged 6-12 years, the pronunciation of sonorants, which already needed speech therapy support, suffered more often. It was found that among the violations of the phonetic side of pronunciation, changes in the pronunciation of a group of sibilants and hissing sounds were most often observed in children with a distal deep bite, dentoalveolar anomalies have virtually no effect on pronunciation. Method and tactics of treatment of children with anomalies and deformations of the dentoalveolar apparatus additional examination methods were used. It was found that with mesial bite parameters are registered indicating a violation of the contractile activity of the masticatory muscles, and the most significant decrease in muscle activity with satisfactory indicators in the temporal. The amplitude of the biopotentials of the orbicularis oris muscle during functioning with a distal complicated deep bite is below the indicators of the relative norm, which indicates characteristic functional disorders accompanying the dentoalveolar anomaly. The study of the state of the muscle component indicates that subject to correction. At the same time, the obtained data help the orthodontist direct treatment taking into account changes in the muscles. An important component of the articulatory apparatus is the tongue. Using cone beam computed tomography, the anatomical and topographic indicators of the tongue and its position were established. In case of a complicated distal deep, distal bite, the root of the tongue is in the posterior lower position, which requires the work of an orthodontist and speech therapist (normally the root is located in the projection of the soft palate)

Taking into account the age of the patients, removable (Schwartz lower or upper jaw, Andresen-Goypl, Bruckl-Reichenbach, Flis P.S.-Filonenko V.V. apparatus for open bite treatment) or fixed orthodontic apparatus (Marco Ross apparatus) were used to eliminate orthodontic pathology, depending on the clinical situation. Most patients had a narrowing of the jaws in the lateral areas. The results of orthodontic treatment by measuring scanned jaw models using a computer program for establishing the sagittal dimensions of the dental arches showed that treatment for 10-12 months using orthodontic structures led to an insignificant decrease in the average length of the anterior section of the upper dental arch with distal (by 1.4 mm), distal

complicated deep. (by 1.1 mm) bite, lower - with mesial (by 1.2 mm), which is explained by the retrusion of the anterior teeth as a result of treatment. The results of determining the transverse dimensions of the dental arches using the Moorrees method showed that the most average expansion in the area of the occlusions was achieved in the upper treatment of distal (3.3 mm), complicated distal deep (2.6 mm) and mesial bite (2.3 mm). Cephalograms were decoded using the Schwarz method using the Radiocef Studio2 computer program, and superimposition of cephalometric images was also performed. Upon completion of treatment, when decoding the cephalograms of the patients' heads, the most informative improvements concerned the placement of the apical base of the lower jaw in relation to the base of the skull in the sagittal direction in the treatment of distal and distal bite, complicated deep vertical position of the jaws in the treatment of open bite. The inclination of the axes of the teeth in relation to the planes of the jaw base improved. After treatment, the patients showed: normalization of bioelectrical activity indicators, a decrease in the number of parafunctional manifestations in the muscles and a decrease in the frequency of spontaneous muscle activity outbreaks in a state of rest; normalization of the average amplitude of biopotentials in a state of activity, absence of fragmentations, improvement of synchronicity and coordination of muscle contraction in all types of bite pathology.

Additionally, at home we used standard vestibular plates «Dr. Hinz – MUPPY-P» with beads, removable orthodontic devices, Bluegrassappliances and the proposed devices having a bracket soldered to two thin-walled cast perforated crowns designed for fixation on temporary canines, in the middle part of which a functional bead is attached. The advantage of the device is as follows: fixation on temporary canines makes the device compact by reducing the size of the structure, which in turn makes hygienic care easier and improves oral hygiene, eliminates the risk of caries in the non-mineralized cervical area at the stage of the unformed root of permanent teeth; promotes the development of kinetic oral praxis, which in turn helps to accelerate the correction of sound pronunciation in speech therapy work; The use of a functionally active element in the form of a bead allows you to control the habitual palatine position of the tongue during the day, which stimulates the muscles of the tongue. 30 patients underwent computed tomography to determine the volume of the airways (paranasal sinuses). The obtained data were processed in the SIMPlant dental graphic program with the construction of panoramic and 3D reconstructions. After orthodontic treatment, using repeated cone-beam computed tomography, it was found that in patients, against the background of the expansion of the upper jaw, a transition of adenoiditis to a mild degree occurred. Consequently, narrowing of the upper jaw leads to forced retention of the tongue in the lower back position. Changes in the transversal indices of the upper jaw lead to expansion of the nasal cavity floor, which results in an increase in the volume of the airways at all levels and a change in the position of the tongue. and positive functional, morphological and aesthetic changes were achieved during orthodontic treatment.

The proposed complex of diagnostic and therapeutic measures allows to increase the effectiveness of orthodontic treatment of children with dentoalveolar anomalies and deformations due to a multidisciplinary approach.

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